

PHYSIOACTIVE LISTENING IN THE AUDITORY LANDSCAPE

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces and examines the concept of physioactive listening (PL), an embodied form of auditory engagement involving physical movement while exploring spatial audio compositions, soundscapes and audio installations. Distinct from traditional physiopassive (seated and stationary) listening common in concert halls, PL emerges from experimental practices, including Happenings, soundwalking, and contemporary immersive audio environments. The paper traces PL's emergence through early non-technological approaches and later technology-dependent implementations, and in this regard it reframes and consolidates extant work that is conceptually allied through PL. Building on theories of embodied cognition and enactive perception, PL emphasises the relationship between sound, body, and space. The concept has several creative and technological implications: it contrasts single-point listening (isomorphism of listening position between composer and listener) to pluriformal sonic experience (multiple possible listening perspectives on the musical work), highlights the importance of interaction with aural architecture, and necessitates non-teleological structures. The outcome is hybrid practice combining elements of composition, installation, and soundscape. The paper also argues that PL facilitates a more perceptually integrated experience of sound than is found in traditional listening contexts and compositional practices.

1. INTRODUCTION: DEFINING PHYSIOACTIVE LISTENING

Physioactive listening (PL) is an active, embodied form of auditory engagement that involves physical movement while exploring auditory landscapes, including real-world soundscapes, immersive audio experiences, and sound installations. This mode of listening can be distinguished from physiopassive listening, where the listener is still, typically seated, and physically constrained in their embodied listening experience – exemplified in traditional concert hall contexts. While both modes are forms of attentive listening, PL engages the listener's body more extensively through spatial exploration and movement. The concept, though building on established practices, is introduced in the doctoral research of Jimi Wilson, Te Kōki New Zealand School of Music (Wellington, New Zealand),

in his practice-based investigation of novel approaches to immersive audio experiences [1]. The term PL is not presented as definitive, but rather is used provisionally as a conceptual tool with which to analyse, explore and experiment with the relationships between sound, space, kinaesthetics and locomotion.

2. ARTISTIC PRECEDENTS AND RELATED PRACTICES

The concept of PL emerges from a rich history of experimental sonic and musical practices spanning the past half-century. Early manifestations appeared in the 1960s counterculture through Allan Kaprow's happenings, which emphasised active audience participation [2]. Perhaps the most direct antecedent is the practice of soundwalking, developed by the World Soundscape Project, where participants actively engage with environmental sound through guided walks [3]. Related approaches include R. Murray Schafer's environmental compositions, such as *Music for Wilderness Lake* [4], which encourage direct interaction between performers, listeners, and the landscape's sounding and non-sounding elements. While Pauline Oliveros' Deep Listening practice, which emerged in the 1970s, typically emphasises stillness, its attention to embodied awareness is significant to understanding physioactive engagement [5].

A contemporary artist whose work furthers these various approaches is Mareike Dobewall, whose research takes a site-specific approach to exploring the scenographic potential of sound and music, for example, in her work *Demmin – letting a city sound* (2020) in which “The audience could walk freely but were guided along the unfolding sound path by the voices of the choir. The audience was explorative and would move around and experience different perspectives during the different parts” [6].

These examples represent a predominantly non-technological approach to PL. A parallel approach demonstrates stronger reliance on sound technologies, exemplified by: Maryanne Amacher's sound characters works, “a form of sonic theatre in which architecture magnifies the sensorial presence of experience. Rooms, walls, and corridors that sing” [7]; Robin Minard's site-specific spatially distributed sound installations; Bill Fontana's telematic installations, which further Amacher's pioneering *City Links series* (1967-), in which he technologically expands the sonic boundaries of PL beyond the immediate listening space; and Christina Kubisch's *Electrical Walks series* (2003-) which are significant for their heightened urban ambulations in which listeners technologically

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“tune” to usually inaudible electromagnetic phenomena [8], [9]. The ambulatory music developed by artists associated with the Institute of Electronic Music and Acoustics (IEM) demonstrates increasing technological sophistication in relation to PL. Notable examples are Gerhard Eckel’s *Among* [10] and Martin Rumori’s *Paris Flaneur* [11], both of which create navigable auditory landscapes and in this regard can be understood as related to *Music Promenade*, Luc Ferrari’s pathfinding exploration of ambulatory listening “in which the walker is free to choose his musical route” [12]. Finally, Gerriet Sharma’s pioneering work with icosahedral loudspeaker (Iko) technology includes production of architecturally responsive sculptural compositions that reward PL [13], [14].

Contemporary manifestations of PL extend into commercial and popular contexts. 4DSOUND [15], for example, has developed immersive audio environments that encourage physical exploration of sound. This approach shares characteristics with electronic dance music environments, where physical movement and sonic engagement are intrinsically linked, albeit with greater emphasis on entrainment than nuanced listening. VR environments, including gaming applications, simulate PL through navigable environments that can be sonically feature rich, though these implementations may encounter VR-specific challenges such as motion sickness, a concern addressed by Wilson in his doctoral research [1].

3. AMBULATORY MUSIC AND SONIC CHOREOGRAPHY

Gerhard Eckel’s *Among* [10], developed as a case study for the collaborative Choreography of Sound research project [16], is a significant antecedent to the concept of PL. There are several aspects to this. Firstly, Eckel describes *Among* as an “ambulatory concert” [10] which the audience can experience through physioactive or physiopassive listening, “concentrated and potentially ambulatory listening”. It is notable that Eckel emphasises concentrated and silent listening, thus identifying *Among* as an extension upon the western concert music tradition with its ethos of silently attentive listening. Secondly, to allow for both physioactive and physiopassive listening, *Among* emerges as a “a hybrid between an installation and a concert” [10]. As will later be shown, this hybridization is crucial to work that supports PL. Thirdly, Eckel introduces the concept of the “space filling texture” [10] as a necessary formal approach allowing for creatively and experientially meaningful engagement with the “sonic multiperspectivity” introduced through a spatially distributed and potentially physioactively experienced work. These three features – ambulation, hybrid form, and sonic multiperspectivity – are foundational to PL.

4. PL AND EMBODIMENT

A key aspect of PL is that it recognises the relationship between sound and music, embodied listening, and the spatially immersive nature of sonic experience. Theories of

embodied listening, such as Mark Leman’s influential *Embodied Music Cognition and Mediation Technology* [17], emphasise coupling of sound/music, cognition, and the body. As Leman understands it, action and perception conjoin in listening, enlisting the human body as a mediator of musical experience which enriches musical understanding and experience. What is not included in such theories of embodied listening however, even when embodied listening extends to dancing [18], is the idea that listening with and through the body can also involve spatial exploration. This most likely reflects conventional understanding of music as an object rather than as an environment or, as the theme of this conference has it, an auditory landscape. Yet in free field listening in natural and built environments, as well as in listening to creative work such as Sharma’s sonic-sculptural works for Iko, or Eckel’s *Among*, or countless spatial audio compositions, the spatially immersive nature of sonic experience is undeniable, calling to mind Tim Ingold’s concept of ensoundment: “Sound, like breath, is experienced as a movement of coming and going, inspiration and expiration. If that is so, then we should say of the body, as it hums, whistles, resonates and vibrates, that it is ensounded” [19]. Building on Leman and Ingold, the concept of PL is not just about *music being in the body* as a mediator of musical experience, it is also about *the body being in the music* or rather *being in sound*. PL couples sound and music, the body, and space, through the investigative and expressive movement of the listener. This is consistent with Alva Noë’s concept of “enactive perception” [20], [21] which posits that perception is not simply a representational mental process, but also a way of actively and physically accessing information in world, and as such is a sensorimotor skill.

Understanding perception as a sensorimotor skill exercised in the context of ensoundment highlights the immersive and multimodal nature of PL. Multimodality is important in immersive experiences, hence the emphasis placed on creating multimodal cues in VR [22]. By contrast, in the monosensory context of acousmatic listening, multimodality can only be evoked in the listener, as Smalley [23] has pointed out. PL however, actualises and integrates hearing with moving, seeing, touching, and smelling. This aligns with Grimshaw-Aagard’s definition of the role of “salient externality” in affording experiential presence in VR: “the environment must perforce comprise models of aspects of externality in order to provide the perceptual space in which my self can attain self-presence. ... The environment comprises percepts that are other-present to my self—self-presence cannot be achieved without the perception of other-presence” [24]. This is not to say that all sensory modalities will align with hearing, after all PL does not (as yet) take place within the kind of hyperreal sensorium for which VR aims. Nonetheless, multimodality is fundamental to PL. This assertion is supported, for example, by recent neurophysiological research demonstrating the significance of cognitive integration of conflicting visual and nonvisual self-motion cues to estimating distance in VR experience: while distance can be estimated from visual information alone, accuracy substantially improves

when both visual and self-motion cues are available [25].

The activation of other (non-auditory) senses, as they are tinted by sound, contributes to the fullness of enactive perception in PL. As North puts it "Fundamental to acoustics and the perception of acoustic spaces, or soundscapes, [is] the interplay of sound wave reflection, resonance and absorption [which] facilitates the subject's orientation of, and interaction with, their environment." [26]. In this way, PL re-introduces the real into the virtual. The net result is a more perceptually integrated experience of sound than is possible in traditional listening contexts, including acousmatic listening in immersive audio environments. In such contexts, listening is primarily a cognitive activity, with embodiment being very restricted, while in PL embodiment becomes a significant feature of listening. Auditory landscapes, composed or natural, are navigable in PL, which is a return to the conditions of natural listening in which sound is periphonic (ensounding), the listener can orientate towards sonic features that are of perceptual interest and explore these through investigative movement. In this way, PL facilitates the exercise of curiosity through physical exploration of the perceptual environment.

5. PL, SPATIALISATION TECHNOLOGIES AND ACCESSIBILITY

Spatial audio technologies for PL could in principle take any form. Using an Iko, or a multichannel system, through which the creation of hyperrealistic spatial imagery is not the paramount concern, appear well suited to PL. An apt example is the GRM Acousmonium with its variegated loudspeaker array and aesthetic of treating loudspeaker pairs as instruments, and also of attending to the influence of aural architecture, both understood as having a determinative role in sound diffusion performance. Such an approach seems better suited to PL than, for example, the BEAST system in which loudspeaker idiosyncracies and room acoustic appear to be subordinate to creation of a cohesive and controllable spatial image. This is not a value judgement, but does point to the differences between creative practices presuming physiopassive listening and those focused on PL, in which it is likely that a highly distributed, variegated, and acoustic-architectural approach to the creation of sonic space will be sought.

Higher order ambisonics (HOA) systems, while certainly adaptable to PL, would need to be approached with more flexibility to engage in expressive use of sweet spot disintegration when listener exploration extends beyond this perceptual Goldilocks zone. This aligns with observations made by Eckel et al concerning HOA in the context of the "choreography of sound" and the possibility of approaching ambisonics "in an experimental way using subgroups of closely related speakers, under-determined or non-ideal speaker layouts, or making various, often hidden parameters of Ambisonics encoding and decoding available for composing" [16].

Beyond these aesthetic and experiential concerns it is also important to note that sound systems suited to PL offer artists without the significant resources of funded research institutions, or the entrepreneurial focus of a com-

pany such as 4DSound, to develop systems in a provisional and non-systematic way using whatever loudspeaker resources can be assembled for a particular project. This recalls DIY practices, such as those of Maryanne Arma-cher's early site-specific aural architectural works [27], as well as the Jamaican sound system tradition [28] and indeed in the sound clash systems which have proliferated globally [29], [30]. A further point concerning accessibility is that listeners with limited mobility may not be able to engage in PL in actual physical spaces. VR, however, provides an alternative platform through which to virtually explore auditory landscapes; this is a strong focus of Wilson's doctoral research [1].

6. CREATIVE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF PL

There are a number of creative and technological consequences of PL. The first of these, as noted by Eckel et al, is that single point listening (a concept introduced by New Zealand composer John Cousins [31]), as a privileged point of audition (POA) and the creation of a sweet spot to enable this, is superseded. Instead, "sonic multiperspectivity" [10] is necessitated, which in turn requires a pluriformal approach to composition. This could be realised in numerous ways, for example, as multiple sweet spots, or dispersal of areas of sonic interest throughout the listening environment (aligned with Eckel's concept of the "space-filling texture"), or as a mobile and labile approach to texture and space. This affords creation of listening environments "which can be perceived from multiple angles or listening positions, each of them provoking a different experience, and all of them forming an integral part of the composition" [16].

Secondly, aural architecture [32] is significant in works created for PL. While it is entirely feasible that the virtual soundfield of an HOA work in a multichannel loudspeaker environment can support PL, it is likely that richer experiential interest will be generated where the acoustic-architectural setting and the work itself are integrated, thus "inscribing sound into a specific hall and setup in such a way, that it allows for taking up many different perspectives that expose musical significance" [16]. Much of Sharma's work with the Iko seeks a similar outcome. By comparison, and as has been noted elsewhere, a conventional approach to spatial audio composition creates a virtual acoustic space and, as much as this is possible, negates or occludes the listening space [33]. While there is nothing inherently wrong with such an approach, it does "flatten" the listening experience by reducing the work to the virtual acoustic image and single point listening, ignoring the space that frames, and often acoustically alters, the work. By contrast, an aural-architectural approach to the creation of auditory landscapes enhances pluriformality and increases the experiential augmentation that can be offered in PL. At very least, in PL practices, the listening space is akin to a frame or plinth, a real object that holds the virtual space in a tensional relationship, a point made by Wilson in examining the relationship between sound and gallery spaces [1]. In any case, the space of listening

is an influencing object, rather than one to be occluded.

Thirdly, in composing for PL the temporality of a work is unlikely to be teleological, that is, markedly linear. This is because if a work is designed for PL it must afford, and reward, engagement with sonic features and events from multiple perspectives (as discussed above). A highly linear work does not allow the attentional time required for such a mode of engagement. Consequently, the PL work is likely to be of a longer duration and be characterised by repetition of materials and/or considerable focus on texture, as conceived by Smalley [23]. This does not preclude compositional linearity, but suggests that materials must be repeated in order to become meaningful in the decentred, pluriformal auditory landscape of a PL work; the temporality of such a work might bear resemblance to the soundscape, through probabilistic iteration of materials, in certain places, within particular intervals of time, as is the case in the soundscape. In the macro-rhythms of soundscapes, natural or anthropogenic, a given “sound event” [34] is more or less likely to be observable at particular times, co-present with other elements of the soundscape. In this sense, the PL work will likely become an environment in which to dwell, and as such, could be understood as a hybrid form, composition-installation-soundscape, a point Eckel also makes [10]. A conceptual route into such work, is Deleuze and Guattari’s notion of the refrain [35], the repetition of an element that through its familiarity establishes “territories”, or “lived rhythms”; as North [26] writes, “Rhythm leads to movement, movement always in time and space”, and points out that while in soundscape composition such movement is representational, the soundwalk, which has been noted as an important waymark to PL, is “itself is a journey, an apparent connection between the soundscape and movement” [26].

7. PL AND FORM

Of particular relevance to PL is the formal openness of soundscape, as investigated by Fisher [36] who presents the problematic of the natural soundscape as follows: “nature does not provide an intentional object of appreciation the way musicians do, there is a serious framing problem concerning the sounds of nature: which sounds do I pay attention to and for how long?”. This problem largely dissolves when objects of listening attention, distributed in time and space as they are in soundscape, can be explored through PL; the attentional activity of the listener, extended to include movement, no longer requires that experiential objects be organised to highlight their significance (think here of motifs, themes, cadences etc), as these can now be located and “hunted” by listeners, whose individual “choreography of sound” [16] creates a singular version of the work through PL. An exemplar is Eckel’s *Zeitraum*, about which he writes: “The audience experiences a spatial sound texture by walking about a concert hall, wondering about the implication of their listening position on the rhythmical patterns they perceive” [10].

As a consequence of such an approach the form of a work becomes open – pluriformal – in contrast to the closed form of traditional composition. In the context of fine arts, par-

ticularly sculpture and installations, this is not novel: the audience’s understanding of the artwork is built up through their particular phenomenological adumbrations of it. In music, which has been dominated by narrativity, PL establishes conditions for the pluriformal work, which affords potentially limitless perspectives on it, pushing the phenomenological notion of adumbration to an extreme given the hypothetically inexhaustible number of ways the physioactive listener can engage with a piece. Needless to say, this presents a considerable change to the work concept, as conceived in the western concert music tradition [37]. Engaging with PL from the outset of the creative process initiates and anticipates “a temporally extended, dynamic exchange with the world around us” [20]. Furthermore, if a work is pluriformal, by virtue of its having been experientially decentred through PL, then there is no reason why works for PL should not be generative, moving beyond the token-type relationship attributed to musical works in the interpretative performance of the musical score [38] (a relationship extendable to diffusion performance of electroacoustic compositions).

8. SOCIAL AND POLITICAL OBSERVATIONS ON PL

In the context of the preceding discussion it is important to briefly touch on some of the social and political implications emerging from PL and the sonic technologies it uses. It can be argued, following the work of Jean Baudrillard (chiefly in *Simulacra and Simulation* [39]), that headphones, surround sound systems (HOA, Dolby Atmos etc.), and VR binaural audio, while potentially able to provide fulsome auditory experiences, nonetheless remove listeners from the real. Indeed, Baudrillard used the example of quadraphonic sound as an early instance of hyperreality [40]; this being the process in which reality is displaced and ultimately replaced by simulations. At an extreme, in hyperreality it is no longer possible to distinguish between reality and simulation, and ushering in what Baudrillard dubbed “the desert of the real” [39]. This is not to cast doubt on the value or aims of artistic use of spatial audio technologies. Rather, it is to critically position artistic use of such technologies in relation to their political and economic context. As Sharma puts it, “who creates these [sonic] environments and with which intentions, and how can music, sound art, and design contribute with their own strategies, to such a reality?” [41], [42]. Consider, long before we reach the extreme of a VR “desert of the real”, the already ubiquitous phenomenon of the “management of everyday life” in headphone listening. Both of these social-technological situations pivot on the manipulation, benign or otherwise, of the relationship between the real and the virtual (or simulation as Baudrillard would have it). What is interesting about PL in this context is that it emphasise and affords reintegration of the real, the virtual, the private, and the social (implicating the political and the economic). PL, in its emphasis on integrated experiential conditions (real and virtual), and open-ended social listening, draws listeners back into an actual, if temporary, community of listeners. Moreover, given the formal and

temporal features of PL works, and the heterogenous experiential outcomes of PL for the audience, the need or desire for communal response to such experiences (through reflection and discussion) is likely to be pronounced. This suggests an alignment between a PL approach and relational aesthetics [43], [44], [45]. In any case, the topics broached in this section warrant further discussion, albeit in another context.

9. EXAMPLE: THE 40 PART MOTET

Janet Cardiff and George Bures Miller's *The 40 Part Motet* [46] will now be briefly discussed to illustrate PL in context. There are a number of Cardiff and Bures Miller's works that could be explicated in relation to PL. For example, their augmented reality audio walks [47] neatly illustrate the experiential interaction between virtual sound (delivered binaurally using headphones) and real environments, with the perceptual gap between the real and the virtual closed through shared acoustic qualities. However, for present purposes, their sound installation, *The 40 Part Motet*, a "reworking" [46] of Thomas Tallis' "Spem in Alium" (1573) 40-part chorale [48], is significant in its leveraging of the key elements of PL. The installation records each of the motet's vocal parts to an individual channel which are reproduced on individual loudspeakers, arranged in an oval ring, in the installation. Listeners can thus experience the recording as an immersive virtual choral performance, if they locate themselves in the middle of the oval. The interaction between the recording and the listening space is vital to creating the aural architecture of a sacred music performance, and establishes a site specificity as each individually recorded voice is contextualised and coloured by the listening space. The audience can also explore the choir through PL, moving close to single loudspeakers to hear individual voices with their unique characteristics. This proximity creates a strong sense of presence that breaks the fourth wall of the concert listening experience and enhances, through intimacy, the affective impact of the installation (which itself relies heavily on the beauty of Tallis' piece). Furthermore, as the 14-minute recording is looped, the audience can experience the installation multi-perspectively, creating through PL an individual experiential choreography through ambulatory exploration of the installation. In these ways the reworking of "Spem in Alium" both encourages and experientially enriches PL.

10. CLOSING REMARKS

Physioactive Listening (PL) significantly departs from conventional modes of sonic engagement and creation, evincing new possibilities for composition, sound installation, and interactive sonic environments. The implications of PL extend beyond artistic practice into wider cultural and technological domains. The proliferation of spatial audio technologies, AR, and VR, suggests that PL will continue to evolve as a dynamic field, fostering new experiences and conceptualisations of sound. PL also raises important considerations for accessibility and inclusivity. As alternative platforms, such as VR, allow those with lim-

ited mobility to explore auditory landscapes, the potential for democratizing immersive sound experiences grows [1]. Fundamentally, PL challenges the privileging of single-point sweet spot listening, as it requires a more integrated, exploratory, and participatory approach to sound. The application of PL principles in urban sound design, public art, and therapeutic practices also suggests impacts beyond explicitly artistic contexts, influencing how we understand, utilise and engage with sound and space in everyday life. In sum, the convergence of technology, artistic practice, and embodied cognition in PL opens up compelling auditory landscapes for future artistic-technological research.

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